

Table 2. Evaluation of *NIL127* BI resistance in upland screening sites.

Site	Line ^a	Predominant lesion type ^b	Final percentage diseased leaf area ^c			RADPC ^d Mean	
			1991	1992	1993	1992	1993
Bangladesh	<i>NIL104</i>	4	55	75	60	21.3	29.2
	<i>NIL127</i>	1	1.5	1.1	1.5	0.3	1.0
Colombia ^e	<i>OsS</i>	4	-	-	-	-	-
	<i>NIL127</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-
Indonesia	<i>OsS</i>	4	-	81.25	100	22.80	42.9
	<i>NIL127</i>	0	-	0.05	0.01	0.11	2.5
Philippines	<i>OsS</i>	4	-	Nd ^f	71.67	Nd	18.17
	<i>NIL127</i>	0	-	Nd	0.57	Nd	0.28

^aIn most cases, *NIL127* (RR) was compared with the recurrent parent, *OsS* (rr). Sometimes, however, a susceptible sibling of *NIL127*, identified above as *NIL104* (rr), was used. *NIL104* and *OsS* are identical for the purposes of this study. ^bSee Table 1 for definition of lesion types. ^cMean of four replications. ^dRADPC = relative area under the disease progress curve; mean of four replications. ^eOnly predominant lesion type data were collected when *NIL127* and *OsS* were screened in Colombia. Tests were conducted for three consecutive seasons in two consecutive years (1992A and B and 1993A). ^fNd = no disease observed at the site in the 1992 wet season due to delay of rain. Susceptible and resistant lines alike failed to develop BI symptoms.

lineages 7 and 14 and susceptible to only three isolates of lineage 4 (Table 1).

To determine the performance of *NIL127* under diverse field conditions, we evaluated this line for BI resistance in upland sites at Joydebpur, Bangladesh; Santa Rosa, Colombia; Sitiung, West Sumatra, Indonesia; and Cavinti, Laguna, Philippines (Table 2). At least two 30-50 cm rows of each line were dry seeded parallel to the prevailing winds between one or two rows of a resistant cultivar. At the leeward end of the plot, two rows of a mixture of susceptible spreader varieties were planted perpendicular to the prevailing winds. Leaf BI severity was evaluated twice a week for 3-4 wk by estimating diseased leaf area (%) on a plot basis. In addition, at least five plants were selected at random at the peak of disease development and were evaluated for lesion type using the 0-5 scale (Table 1). The experiments were replicated three or four times. Means were calculated from the replications.

We previously observed that *NIL127* remained BI-free when planted in the IRRI blast nursery and in lowland field plots on the IRRI farm (data not shown). *NIL127* was also resistant to field populations of BI in all upland screening sites where it was tested. At the Santa Rosa, Colombia site, for example, six lineages are known to be present, yet the line has remained resistant for three seasons. Hypersensitive lesions were observed (type 0 or 1), although it was

not possible to obtain any viable BI isolates from them. On the other hand, lesions on the recurrent parent, *OsS*, were usually type 4 (susceptible) (Table 2).

Comparative transmission of two strains of rice tungro spherical virus in the Philippines

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A virulent strain of rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV), designated as strain Vt6, was found to be infecting rice plants in Midsayap, North Cotabato, Philippines. The strain could highly infect rice cultivar TKM6, which is highly resistant to the IRRI strain of RTSV, designated as strain A. We conducted comparative transmission tests to identify varieties with resistance to both strains.

We tested rice accessions from the International Rice Germplasm Center for their reaction to strain Vt6. Selected accessions had been previously identified as resistant to strain A but were susceptible to green leafhopper (GLH) according to the IRRI Entomology Unit's data base on GLH resistance. Virus-free adult GLH were given 4 d of access to rice cultivar Taichung Native 1 (TN1) infected with both rice tungro bacilliform

We conclude from these studies that *NIL127* performs well under BI stress at a variety of sites. Although the resistance in *NIL127*, presumably contributed by a resistance gene from *O. minuta* in the IR31917-45-3-2 background, may not be effective against artificial inoculation with some lineage 4 isolates, *NIL127* functions effectively in the field. The apparent susceptibility of *NIL127* to some isolates in greenhouse tests suggests that this wild species-derived resistance gene is not likely to condition durable resistance alone, although it may be a useful component in a gene pyramiding program.

For further evaluation or for use in breeding programs, *NIL127* seeds can be requested from the International Network for Genetic Evaluation in Rice under the line number WHD-IS-75-1-127. This line will be included in the International Rice Blast Nursery core collection in 1994. ■

virus and strain Vt6. Three GLH were confined for 24 h with a 6-d-old seedling in a test tube for inoculation access.

Forty seedlings (2 replications, 20 seedlings/replication) were inoculated for each variety. Inoculated seedlings were transplanted into pots and grown in screened cages until symptoms developed. An identical set of test varieties simultaneously inoculated with strain A in the same manner served as control. Rice tungro viruses were indexed by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay 1 mo after inoculation.

Results showed that all of the varieties tested were resistant to strain A except for Utri Rajapan, which showed an intermediate reaction. Their reaction to strain Vt6, however, varied from highly resistant (0-10% infection ratio) to very susceptible. Twenty-nine varieties had an infection rate of more than 60%, comparable with susceptible check TN1 (see table). These results contradict our previous view that virus resistance is more durable than vector resistance.

Eleven leafhopper-susceptible accessions were highly resistant to both strains. These accessions may be used as sources

Comparative transmission of two RTSV strains.

IRGC ¹ Acc. no.	Variety name	RTSV infection (%)		IRGC ² Acc. no.	Variety name	RTSV infection (%)	
		Strain A	Strain Vt6			Strain A	Strain Vt6
177	Adday Sel.	0	0	27779	Bara Pashawari	390	0
180	Adday Local Sel.	0	0	27787	Basmati Nahani	381	13
237	TKM6	0	59	27798	Basmati 1	10	100
10262	G378	0	100	27818	Basmati 242	0	29
11751	Habiganj DW8	0	26	27829	Basmati 377	3	82
12274	ARC6561	7	100	27830	Basmati 388	11	94
12428	ARC10312	0	93	27832	Basmati 405	0	97
12437	ARC10343	0	78	27833	Basmati 406	0	13
12765	Kataribhog	5	74	27836	Basmati 433	0	98
14504	IR580 420-1-1-2	4	58	27856	Begumi 302	10	18
14527	Barah	0	41	27869	Chahora 144	3	100
16680	Utri Merah	0	3	27870	Chahora 148	0	83
16684	Utri Rajapan	38	79	27872	Chahora 292	0	97
19680	ARC10963	0	68	27873	Chahora 382	0	100
20600	ARC7321	0	18	27946	Hansraj 62	0	100
21310	ARC11315	0	80	27947	Hansraj 189	0	100
21474	ARC11555	0	14	27951	Hansraj 365A	0	92
21745	ARC11920	0	8	28102	P590	0	92
21958	ARC12170	3	94	28522	Gundrikbhog	0	50
22199	ARC12620	0	51	28867	Aus 4	0	100
22215	ARC12636	0	15	36731	Firro E(1)	0	16
22307	ARC12746	0	52	37215	Matichakma	0	67
22331	ARC12778	0	28	37337	Urman Sardar	0	51
26253	Nep Bap	0	8	37482	Konekchul	0	92
26410	Pala Bhir	3	3	37761	Maliabhangor 1096	0	3
26495	Konek Chul	3	8	49996	Ovarikondoh	0	3
26527	Shull 2	0	86	11355	IR20 ^b	0	16
26582	Buchi 2	0	100	24153	IR26 ^b	0	8
26791	Sham Rosh	0	3	30413	IR30 ^b	0	6
26813	Gogoj	0	3	21473	ARC11554 ^b	0	0
105	Taichung Native 1	98	95				

¹IRGC = International Rice Germplasm Center. ²Vector-resistant variety. Other varieties are susceptible to GLH after IRR1 data base on GLH resistance.

of resistance genes to both strains of RTSV. Information on the occurrence of virus strains in different regions is needed

for effective deployment of resistance genes. ■

Symptomatic strains of rice tungro bacilliform virus

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Several tungro virus strains have been reported previously. Most of these reports, however, were published long before the discovery that two viruses are involved in the disease. Hence, the reported strains could be interpreted as being due to either infection with one or both viruses. From an isolate maintained in a greenhouse, we isolated four rice

tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) strains by separating them from rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). Differential cultivars, TN1 and FK135, were serially inoculated with the strains, using *Nephotettix virescens*, until consistent symptoms were obtained.

The RTBV strains (Ic, G1, and G2) were differentiated from the type strain (L) by the symptoms they cause on FK135 and TN1. On FK135, strain Ic induced distinct interveinal chlorosis, stunting, reduced tillering, and narrow leaves, whereas G1 and G2 caused only

mild stunting, with foliage remaining normal and green. Symptoms caused by these strains were milder than those caused by strain L, which induces very severe stunting and interveinal chlorosis (Fig. 1a). On TN1, Ic and G1 caused mild stunting and foliage remained green in contrast with G2, which caused severe stunting and discoloration similar to the type strain (Fig. 1b).

Cross-inoculation experiments showed that strains G1 and Ic were cross-protective. FK135 plants infected with G1 did not show changes in symptom pattern when challenge-inoculated with Ic 1 or 2 wk after inoculation with G1, and vice versa. When virus-free green leafhoppers were allowed to access cross-inoculated plants for 24 h and used to inoculate FK135 seedlings, only the strain inoculated first was transmitted. Cross protection was incomplete when challenge inoculation was done at a 1-d interval. Most of the inoculated plants, however, showed the symptoms of the strain inoculated first. Both strains were recovered from these plants, but more of the strain inoculated first (see table).

These results indicate that RTBV is variable. The difference in symptom expression of the strains on TN1 and FK135 indicated that at least two viral

Cross-inoculation between RTBV strains G1 and Ic at different time intervals and virus recovery from cross-inoculated plants 1 mo after the second inoculation.

Interval between inoculations	Inoculation sequence ^a	Plants (no.) with symptoms ^b of		Strains re-covered ^c (no.)	
		1st	2d	1st	2d
2 wk	G1 Ic	19	0	94	0
	Ic G1	17	0	69	0
1 wk	G1 Ic	33	0	129	0
	Ic G1	17	0	88	0
1 d	G1 Ic	46	5	120	38
	Ic G1	39	4	111	14
Control	G1 None	17	0	30	0
	Ic None	17	0	61	0

^aFive viruliferous leafhoppers were confined with 2-wk-old FK135 plants for 24-h inoculation access. ^bBased on presence or absence of interveinal chlorosis 1 mo after the second inoculation. ^cVirus-free leafhoppers were allowed 24 h access to cross-inoculated plants showing symptoms of the 1st virus and used to inoculate 6-d-old FK135 seedlings. Plants were scored 1 mo after inoculation.